

Magnetic and Spectroscopic Studies on Some Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Schiff Base Complexes Derived from Vanillin and Aromatic Amines

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Eight planar or octahedral complexes of sulphates of copper(II) and nickel(II) with four Schiff bases viz., vanillideneaniline, vanillidene-*o*-toluidine, vanillidene-*m*-toluidine and vanillidene-*p*-toluidine have been prepared. The complexes contain two molecules of the Schiff base which function as a monodentate ligand coordinating through only its azomethine group while the rest of the positions in the coordination geometry of the metal(II) ions are occupied by water molecules. The magnetic and spectroscopic data of the complexes are discussed in the light of structures assigned.

THE Schiff bases, which comprise a well known group of nitrogen donors, have been extensively used for complex formation in the past few years and a large number of different aldehydes and amines have been used. Vanillin or hydroxy or methoxy aldehydes have, however, been comparatively less studied¹⁻⁴. In the present investigation a systematic study of four Schiff bases, all derived from vanillin and aromatic amines, and their complexes with copper(II) and nickel(II) sulphates are reported. The structures of the complexes have been established using analytical, conductance, magnetic, infrared and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

The title ligands have the general structure

They have been obtained by the following method.

One equivalent of vanillin in methanol was taken in a flask and one equivalent of amine in the same solvent was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hr. The excess solvent was distilled off and the Schiff base crystallised from petroleum spirit (40-60°). The individual Schiff bases are listed below, along with their melting points and analytical data.

1. *Vanillideneaniline* : C₁₄H₁₃O₂N, dark yellow, m.p. 101°, (Found : C, 74.32 ; H, 6.02 ; N, 5.89. Calcd. ; C, 74.00 ; H, 5.72 ; N, 6.16%).

2. *Vanillidene-*o*-toluidine* : C₁₅H₁₅O₂N(*o*), light brown, m.p. 101°, (Found : C, 74.24 ; H, 6.42 ; N, 5.61. Calcd. ; C, 74.68 ; H, 6.22 ; N, 5.80%).

3. *Vanillidene-*m*-toluidine* : C₁₅H₁₅O₂N(*m*), light brown, m.p. 104°, (Found : C, 74.32 ; H, 6.54 ; N, 6.02%).

4. *Vanillidene-*p*-toluidine* : C₁₅H₁₅O₂N(*p*), brown, m.p. 107°, (Found : C, 74.48 ; H, 6.62 ; N 5.98%).

The complexes have been prepared by refluxing metal(II) sulphates with the appropriate Schiff base in stoichiometric amount in methanol for 4 to 5 hr. Methanol was distilled off and the complex so obtained was recrystallised from ethanol and petroleum ether repeatedly. The colour, analytical, molar conductance and magnetic moment data are given in Table 1.

Conductivity of the complexes was measured on a Philips PR 9500 magic eye type instrument. Infrared spectra were recorded in the form of nujol mulls on a Perkin Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer in the 4000-400 cm⁻¹ range. Magnetic moments were measured by standard Gouy method on finely powdered samples. The electronic spectra were recorded on a VSU-2P spectrometer in the 220-1100 nm range in the form of nujol mulls.

Results and Discussion

The molecular formulae of the complexes have been obtained from the analytical data (Table 1). The molar conductance values indicate that all the complexes behave as electrolytes, breaking up into two ions. The copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes are thus assigned the formulae [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₂] SO₄.

TABLE I

Complex	Colour	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)					Loss of \bar{H}_2O at 280°	Molar cond. mhos	μ_{eff} B. M.
		M	O	H	N	SO ₄			
1. $[Cu(C_{14}H_{14}O_2N)_2(H_2O)_2]SO_4$	Green	10.02 (9.77)	52.10 (51.73)	4.98 (4.61)	4.86 (4.31)	15.02 (14.78)	6.12 (5.54)	25.70	1.71
2. $[Cu(o-C_{14}H_{14}O_2N)_2(H_2O)_2]SO_4$	Green	9.98 (9.55)	52.89 (52.37)	5.21 (4.96)	4.62 (4.21)	14.82 (14.44)	5.92 (5.41)	23.20	1.75
3. $[Cu(m-C_{14}H_{14}O_2N)_2(H_2O)_2]SO_4$	Dirty green	9.82	52.88	5.32	4.86	14.65	6.02	22.80	1.84
4. $[Cu(p-C_{14}H_{14}O_2N)_2(H_2O)_2]SO_4$	Light green	9.75	52.98	5.18	4.96	14.72	6.12	26.98	1.79
5. $[Ni(C_{14}H_{14}O_2N)_2(H_2O)_2]SO_4$	Brown	8.96 (8.62)	50.05 (49.36)	5.26 (4.99)	4.54 (4.11)	14.46 (14.10)	11.01 (10.57)	insoluble	2.86
6. $[Ni(o-C_{14}H_{14}O_2N)_2(H_2O)_2]SO_4$	Dark pink	8.62 (8.28)	51.23 (50.79)	5.48 (5.36)	4.21 (3.95)	13.88 (13.54)	10.84 (10.15)	24.80	3.07
7. $[Ni(m-C_{14}H_{14}O_2N)_2(H_2O)_2]SO_4$	Maroon	8.39	51.29	5.86	4.11	13.73	10.49	23.80	2.91
8. $[Ni(p-C_{14}H_{14}O_2N)_2(H_2O)_2]SO_4$	Yellow- ish brown	8.54	50.26	5.05	4.31	13.92	10.43	insoluble	2.99

and $[Ni(L)_2(H_2O)_4]SO_4$ where L = vanillideneaniline, vanillidene-*o*-toluidine, vanillidene-*m*-toluidine and vanillidene-*p*-toluidine. The presence of coordinated water in the complexes is indicated by the TGA data where loss of weight corresponding to two or four molecules of water, respectively, occurs at 300° (lattice water is lost around 60-80°). Definite evidence for coordination is obtained by infrared data as discussed below.

(i) All the complexes contain a very broad band around 3400 cm^{-1} assigned to the νOH , which normally occurs at 3500 cm^{-1} . Its negative shift indicates coordination⁵.

(ii) The Schiff base ligands as is apparent, contain only one site of coordination which is the azomethine link. The relative placement of the hydroxy and methoxy groups in the ring is such that these are not available for coordination. The evidence that the OH group is not deprotonated is obtained from the fact that sulphate ions are attached and further that the complexes behave as electrolytes (The deprotonation of OH will form a uninegative ligand and hence would have resulted in non-electrolytic complexes).

The free ligand has one strong band around 1665 cm^{-1} which is assigned to the azomethine stretch⁶⁻⁹. In the complexes, however, this band is split into two strong peaks at 1685 ± 20 and 1620 ± 20 cm^{-1} . The former band appears in the same range as for unconjugated systems and hence is the actual $>C=N-$ stretch, while the lower band is attributed to $>C=N-$ coupled with $>C=C<$ stretch. This type of splitting and shifting of the band to higher frequency is reported for those monodentate Schiff base complexes which contain an acidic group (such as hydroxy or methoxy) in the same ring as the donor nitrogen¹⁰⁻¹¹. The increase in frequency of the former band indicates the simultaneous strengthening of the $>C=N-$ bond due to an increase in both sigma overlap and electrostatic attraction, which is possible on account of the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to metal(II) ion. The other

ligand bands remain intact showing that these are not involved in complexation.

(iii) The free sulphate ion (point group Td) gives two characteristic vibrations, ν_3 and ν_4 . Its involvement in coordination lowers the frequency (point group C_{3v}) and hence the ν_1 and ν_2 modes which are otherwise Raman active, appear in the spectra. In all the complexes, only two sharp bands are seen at 1140 and 650 cm^{-1} due to ν_3 and ν_4 modes, whose position confirms that the ion is not coordinated¹².

These infrared data support the formulae assigned to the complexes in which the coordination number of the copper(II) and nickel(II) is four and six, respectively. On the basis of magnetic and electronic spectral data the former are assigned planar and the latter octahedral structures.

Copper(II) complexes : The μ_{eff} values lie in the range 1.74-1.85 B.M. and indicate the presence of a single unpaired electron. In the electronic spectra, one broad main band is seen around 14.38 kK with two shoulders at 19.20 kK and 11.76 kK. These spectra are similar to those of other planar complexes of copper(II) and the bands may be assigned as ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions, respectively. The Dq value is also around 1450 cm^{-1} in all the complexes¹³⁻¹⁴.

Nickel(II) complexes : The magnetic moments values of these complexes fall in the range 2.86-3.07 B.M. corresponding to spin free state. The three bands characteristic of octahedral geometry are seen around 9.80 kK, 14.00 kK and 24.00 kK. These are assigned as, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_3) transitions, respectively. The ν_2 band is invariably split into two components on account of the presence of mixed ligand field which lowers the symmetry to pseudo octahedral. The values of Dq, B, and the ratio ν_2/ν_1 which are around 980, 880 cm^{-1} and 1.65, respectively, are in good agreement with the same of other similar complexes¹⁵⁻¹⁶.

The Dq values for the complexes are only slightly higher than that for $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$ ions and suggest that the Schiff bases used in the study are slightly stronger than water and are thus able to cause its replacement. The nephelauxetic ratio lies around 0.82 corresponding to a high degree of covalency on the complexes.

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